

**Characteristics of Sea Surface Temperature
During the passage of Cyclone *Phailine*.**

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ABSTRACT

In Indian Ocean Bay of Bengal is the area experiencing largest number of cyclones compared to other parts, impacting property damage and human loss. *Phailine* is the cyclone that blow over Bay of Bengal and that happened on 2013 October. Sea Surface temperature has an important role in formation and intensification of cyclone. Cyclone develop only in warm water body and for which SST should be more than 26 °C. Warm water give energy for the development of Cyclone, when the water warm it make evaporation and its release latent heat and give energy to the atmosphere. We analyses changes in SST during passage of Cyclone Phailine and we found a cooling effect after the passage and strength of Cyclone is going to decrease due to cooling effect.

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